

IMPLEMENTATION OF EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN THE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SAN NARCISO, QUEZON

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 8

Pages: 1281-1287

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2912

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14637407

Manuscript Accepted: 12-19-2024

Implementation of Extracurricular Activities in the Secondary Schools in San Narciso, Quezon

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the implementation of extracurricular activities in the secondary school in San Narciso, Quezon. The study involved 60 respondents from a private school and public school located in San Narciso, Quezon. The researcher used questionnaires to gather reliable data to be answered by the target respondents. The descriptive method was used to gather the data needed to determine the implementation of extracurricular activities in the secondary School in San Narciso, Quezon. Most of the respondents are 25-35 years old (67%), 25% are 36-45 years old, and 46 years old and above are remaining 8% which describes that most of the respondents are 25-35 years old.. Nearly every one of them are female 67% and 33% are male which describes that most of the teacher- respondents are female. Under type of school, 82% are public school and 18% are private schools which describe that most of the of the respondents are from public schools. Under educational attainment, 62% are bachelor degree and 32% are masteral degree holder and the remaining 6% are doctoral which describes that most of the respondents are bachelor degree. Under length of service, 45% are in the range of 6-10 years, 43% are 1-5 years and the remaining 12% are 11 years and above which describes that most of the respondents have 6-10 years length of service. The result shows that in the implementation of extracurricular activities in term of IATF Protocol, most of the respondents agreed that the participant should keep their hand clean when participating extracurricular activities with a mean of 4.53. Under DepEd Policy, schools must ensure the strict observance of the guidelines during the conduct of extracurricular activities with a mean 4.55. Under School Policy, student must attend the class discussion as scheduled in school. Meanwhile, there is a significant difference in the response of teacher that have different educational attainment and different length of service.

Keywords: *DepEd Policy, extracurricular activities, IATF protocol, implementation, school policy*

Introduction

DepEd order No. 34, s. 2022 re: School Calendar and Activities for School Year 2022-2023 ensuring that all schools shall adhere to the number of school days required to implement the curriculum including co-curricular activities throughout the school year. Curricular activities shall be conducted during the academic quarter to ensure that learners can seamlessly connect and integrate learning within and across learning areas providing manageable breaks consistent with Memorandum OUCI-20220-307 entitled Suggested measures to Foster academic Ease during the Covid-19 Pandemic. On the other hand, co-curricular activities shall be conducted after the quarter examinations to avoid disruption of classes.

Persuant to the objectives of Sulong Edukalidad, schools shall strictly devote ten weeks of every academic quarter to actual classroom teaching. The eleventh week of each quarter may be used for the conduct of co-curricular activities. The Central Office, Regional Offices, Schools Division Offices (SDOs), and other concerned external stakeholders that need to introduce co-curricular activities, may do so in accordance with this provision on scheduling the same.

Activities that require the participation of learners and teachers that will result in the disruption of classes are strictly prohibited. Activities such as, but not limited to, academic competitions, sports meets, and other contests, including the practices and training of such activities, shall be allowed on the condition that they will be held outside class hours, on weekends, or during school breaks, as provided in DO. No. 9 s. 2005 or instituting Measures to Increase Engaged Time-On-Tasks and Ensuring Compliance Therewith.

Extracurricular activities are just that, extra to the curriculum. In the case of education, extracurricular activities can enhance daily-taught subject areas or individual interests. These activities could include sports, dance, theater, crafting, speech/debate, or cooking, to name a few. In a normal situation, pre-COVID-19, all extracurricular activities for students took place in a school environment without many restrictions, specially protocols that involved health safety.

Extracurricular activities of ten cost money to participate in some type of arranged “play-to-play” fee. Caring adults should consider working with the community to help reduce financial barriers to participation in healthy extracurricular for students to develop skills.

A common problem for many students involved in extracurricular activities is that they take on too much. Students should make out a schedule in advance of a semester that balances school, work, after-school activities, and home life. Also activities should be fun rather than stressful for students. School grades should not suffer because of time spent at work or in after-school activities.

In sports, injuries are not uncommon but can sometimes be prevented with proper conditioning. every child who plans to participate in organized athletic activity should have a pre-season sports physical.

The researcher chose to study the implementation of extracurricular activities because when the pandemic hit many circumstances

arrived that change a lot in conducting extracurricular activities. Nowadays it seems that there is a need to give importance on how to address the problems on the implementation of extracurricular activities so that students will be able to experience a well planned and well designed activities. So, the researcher expect them to be aware on the problems encountered on the implementation of extracurricular activities.

Research Questions

This study determined the implementation of extracurricular activities in the secondary schools in San Narciso, Quezon. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. type of school;
 - 1.4. educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. length of service?
2. What are the implementation of extracurricular activities with respect to:
 - 2.1. IATF protocols;
 - 2.2. DepEd policy; and
 - 2.3. school policy?
3. What are the problems encountered in the implementation of extracurricular activities in terms of:
 - 3.1. teacher factor?
4. Is there a significant difference on the perceived problems encountered in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to profile?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive survey method to collect data for the measure of the implementation of extracurricular activities in secondary schools. The researcher used survey questionnaire as an instrument. Based on the survey's result the researcher determined the details of the study. Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. It can answer what, where and when and how questions, but not why questions. A descriptive research design can use a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables (McCombes, 2019).

Respondents

The researcher selected 60 respondents through proportionate random sampling who are Secondary High School teachers in the SY 2022-2023 and the implementation of extracurricular activities was the focus of the study. The respondents are composed of 60 secondary high school teachers. Proportionate random sampling is a randomly selected subset of a population. In this sampling method, each member of the population has exactly equal chance of being selected. This method is the most straightforward of all the probability sampling methods, since it only involves a single random selection and requires little advance knowledge about the population. (Lauren Thomas, 2020).

Instrument

The researcher used questionnaire. This questionnaire is a Likert scale of ; 5 – Very much Agree (VMA), 4 – Much Agree (MA), 3 – Moderately Agree (MOA), 2 – Less Agree (LA) and 1 – Least Agree (LEA), for understanding about the implementation of extracurricular activities in secondary schools of selected secondary teachers of San Narciso, Quezon. The researcher prepared questionnaire and is composed of demographic profile of the respondents and the implementation of Extracurricular activities, in terms of IATF Protocol, DepEd Policy, School Policy and problems encountered in extracurricular activities in terms of Teacher Factor. A pilot testing was conducted to 12 respondents who are not the target respondents of the study using Cronbach's alpha. After the computation, the result was 0.87 which is interpreted as acceptable. This means that the questionnaire used was reliable.

Procedure

Target populations were the Secondary teachers in San Narciso, Quezon. The descriptive research method using Likert scale was used in order to rate the implementation of extracurricular activities. Data were gathered through "proportionate random sampling". Both male and female teachers of secondary schools in San Narciso, Quezon were selected to fill the questionnaire.

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the principals of Secondary Schools. Upon approval, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher used the time allotted for vacant time to avoid distraction of class discussion. The teachers were given enough time to answer the questions. After data gathering, the researcher collected them for tallying the scores

and to apply the statistical treatment used in the study.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for analysis. They were tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency were used to interpret the profile of the respondents. To test the significant difference of three or more means, the researcher used the Kruskal-Wallis for non-parametric test.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data. All the data gathered were presented here in tabulated form with corresponding interpretation.

The first part described the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, type of school, educational attainment and length of service. The second part are the problems encountered on the implementation of extracurricular activities in the Secondary School in San Narciso, Quezon.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
25-35 yrs old	40	67
36-45 yrs old	15	25
46 yrs old and above	5	8
Total	60	100

Table 1 shows frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to age, where 67% are 25-35 years old and 25% are 36-45 years old and 46 years old and above are the remaining 8%, which describes that most of the respondents are 25-35 years old.

Sivasakthi and Muthumanickam (2012) found that younger teachers of age 30 years old and below, mature or middle age teachers of between 30 to 40 years old and older teachers of above 40 years old do not differ significantly in their teacher effectiveness which indicates that age, regardless of young or mature or older teachers does not make any difference to teacher effectiveness.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Female	40	67
Male	20	33
Total	60	100

Table 2 shows frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to sex, where 67% are female and 33% are male, which describes that most of the teacher-respondents are female. Carington et al. (2008) found that teacher gender had no effect on student achievement.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to type of School*

<i>Type of School</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Public	49	82
Private	11	18
Total	60	100

Table 3 presents the frequency and distribution of the respondents according to type of school in which 82% are from public school and 18% are from private schools, which describe that most of the respondents are from public schools.

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Educational attainment*

<i>Educational attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Bachelor Degree	37	62
Masteral	19	32
Doctoral	4	6
Total	60	100

Table 4 shows frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to educational attainment where 62% have bachelor degree and 32% are masteral degree holder and the remaining 6% are doctoral which describes that most of the respondents are bachelor degree. Slater et al. (2012) mentioned that teacher's higher academic qualifications may not necessarily result in student's performance.

Table 5. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Length of service*

<i>Length of service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1-5 years	26	43
6-10 years	27	45
11 years and above	7	12
Total	60	100

Table 5 presents frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to length of service where 45% are in the range of 6-10 years, 43% are 1-5 years and the remaining 12% are 11 years and above which describes that most of the respondents are 6-10 years length of service. For Fatima and Tugay (2015) teachers with a minimum of ten years of teaching experience are more effective in teaching and good in classroom management skills.

Table 6. *Implementation of Extracurricular Activities in the Secondary School in terms of IATF Protocol*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Maintain a distance of at least 1 meter.	4.15	Much Agree
2. Wear a mask indoors, and outdoors when physical distancing is not possible.	4.15	Much Agree
3. Keep hands clean.	4.53	Very Much Agree
4. Participating in extracurricular activities, the student should have been vaccinated.	4.32	Very Much Agree
5. Stay at home when feeling unwell.	4.7	Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.37	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Table 6 shows the implementation of extracurricular activities in term of IATF Protocol. As shown in the table, respondents very much agreed that, every teacher are agree that the participant should keep their hand clean when participating extracurricular activities with the mean of 4.53. The lowest mean is indicator 5, because of the implementation of extracurricular activities they cannot participate when they are not feeling well with the mean of 4.7. It also revealed that the average mean of total respondents is 4.37 which means very much agree.

Table 7. *Implementation of Extracurricular Activities in the Secondary School in terms of DepEd Policy*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The conduct of in-person extracurricular activities shall be allowed, provided that these activities are conducted after class hours.	4.25	Very Much Agree
2. Extracurricular activities shall be conducted after the quarterly examination.	4.22	Much Agree
3. Schools must ensure the strict observance of the guidelines during the conduct of extracurricular activities.	4.55	Very Much Agree
4. Extracurricular and co-curricular activities that involve the in-person gathering of a number of participants shall be allowed.	4.42	Very Much Agree
5. Department of Education reiterates that all school days shall be solely dedicated to academics and co-curricular activities.	4.5	Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.39	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Table 7 shows the problems encountered on the implementation of extracurricular activities. The high gain of the mean is the indicator number 3, Schools must ensure the strict observance of the guidelines during the conduct of extracurricular activities with a mean 4.55 very much agree. The lowest weighted mean is indicator 5, Department of Education reiterates that all school days shall be solely dedicated to academics and co-curricular activities with a mean 4.5 much agree. It also revealed that the average weighted mean of total respondents is 4.39 which means very much agree.

To ensure the safe resumption and reintroduction of the conduct of in-person school activities, it also said that the school should make sure that they are consistent with the public health standards of the government. DepEd (2023). Director Leila Areola (2022) said that all co-curricular activities have been designed to divert their attention from pandemic. The involvement in the said activities will help them become tougher and prevent mental health issues.

Table 8. *Implementation of Extracurricular Activities in the Secondary School in terms of School Policy*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Student must attend the class discussion as scheduled in school.	4.87	Very Much Agree
2. Students must submit all the requirements and assignment given by their teachers.	4.9	Much Agree
3. Student must have a permission from their parents allowing them to participate in extracurricular activities.	4.9	Much Agree
4. Students must follow all the healthy protocol when participating in extracurricular activities.	4.9	Much Agree
5. Before participating in extracurricular activities the student must be in a good condition.	4.83	Very Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.88	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Table 8 shows the implementation of extracurricular activities. The high gain of the mean is the indicator number 1, Student must attend the class discussion as scheduled in school with the weighted mean 4.87 very much agree. The lowest mean is indicator 4, Students must follow all the healthy protocol when participating in extracurricular activities with a weighted mean 4.9 much agree. It also revealed that the average weighted mean of total respondents is 4.88 which means very much agree.

Item 33 of DepEd Order No. 034, s. 2022 provides that the conduct of extracurricular activities shall be strictly prohibited. The conduct of in-person extracurricular activities shall be allowed, provided that these activities are conducted after class hours.

Table 9. *Problems Encountered in the Implementation of Extracurricular Activities in the Secondary School in terms of Teacher Factor*

Indicators		Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.	Teachers professional abilities are not co-exist.	3.8	Moderately Agree
2.	Teachers attitude can make students to participate in the extracurricular activities.	4.32	Very Much Agree
3.	Teachers not giving attention of knowing the strengths and weaknesses of those students who participate in extracurricular activities.	3.2	Moderately Agree
4.	Teachers believe that the attention of the students will be divided when participating in the extracurricular activities.	3.42	Much Agree
5.	Teachers are not showing full support to those students who participate in extracurricular activities.	2.98	Moderately Agree
Grand Mean		3.54	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

Table 9 shows the problems encountered on the implementation of extracurricular activities . The high gain of the mean is the indicator number 2, Teachers attitude can make students to participate in the extracurricular activities with the weighted mean 4.32 very much agree. The lowest mean is indicator 5, Teachers are not showing full support to those students who participate in extracurricular activities with a weighted mean 2.98 moderately agree. It also revealed that the average weighted mean of total respondents is 3.54 which means much agree.

A positive school culture and high quality teachers are both important factors in a school functioning and helping students find success. Hensch (2020).

Table 10. *Summary Table on the perceived Implementation of Extracurricular Activities in the Secondary School*

The Implementation Of Extracurricular Activities	Average Mean	Verbal Interpretation
IATF Protocol	4.37	Very Much Agree
DepEd Policy	4.39	Very Much Agree
School Policy	4.88	Very Much Agree
Teacher Factors	3.54	Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.30	Very Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree(2.61-3.40), Agree(3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree(4.21-5.0)

The summary table shows the average mean and verbal interpretation of school policy with a mean of 4.88 which means very much agree, DepEd policy with a mean of 4.39 which means very much agree, IATF Protocol with 4.37 mean which means very much agree, and teacher factors with a mean of 3.54 which means much agree. This implies that school policy got the high gain from the given the implementation of extracurricular activities in the Secondary school in San Narciso, Quezon.

Table 11. *Significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to age*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
25-35 years old	40	4.30	2	0.036	0.05	Reject Ho
36-45 years old	15	4.50				
46 years old and above	5	3.90				

The data in Table 11 illustrates significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to age, the p-value of 0.036, leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

This indicates that there is a significant difference in the perception of teachers from different age brackets. Those aged 25-35, 36-45, and 46 years old and above have distinct perceptions of the implementation of extracurricular activities.

Table 12. *Significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to sex*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
Male	20	4.55	1	0.283	0.05	Accept Ho
Female	40	4.23				

Table 12 displays the significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to sex. The p-value of 0.283 at 0.05 level of significance resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is no significant difference in the responses of male and female concerning the implementation of extracurricular activities.

Table 13. *Significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to type of school*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
Private	11	4.10	1	0.029	0.05	Reject Ho
Public	49	4.50				

The information presented in Table 13 highlights significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to type of school. The H value of 4.743 is greater than the critical value of 3.841 at 0.05 level of significance resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is a significant difference in the responses of teachers from the private school and teachers from the public school in the implementation of extracurricular activities.

Table 14. *Significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to educational attainment*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
Bachelor's Degree	37	4.25	2	0.227	0.05	Accept Ho
Masteral Degree	19	4.50				
Doctoral Degree	4	4.03				

Table 14 shows the significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to educational attainment. The H value of 2.969 is smaller than the critical value of 5.991 at 0.05 level of significance resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This suggests that there is no significant difference in the responses of teachers that have different educational attainment in the implementation of extracurricular activities.

Table 15. *Significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to length of service*

Groups	N	Median	df	P - value	Significant Level	Decision
1-5 years	26	4.33	2	0.031	0.05	Reject Ho
6-10 years	27	4.50				Ho
11 years & above	7	3.90				

Table 15 reveals the significant differences in the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to their length of service. The H value of 6.943 is greater than the critical value of 5.991 at 0.05 level of significance resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is a significant difference in the responses of teachers that have different length of service in the implementation of extracurricular activities.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are derived:

Most of the respondents are female, 25-35years old, from Public schools, Bachelor's Degree, 6-10 years length of service.

Among the four categories consisting the implementation of extracurricular activities, School Policy gained a highest mean. Thus, it indicates that it greatly contributes to the implementation of extracurricular activities. This was to conclude that school policy are one of the most in implementing of extracurricular activities.

There is significant difference the implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to age, type of school, and length of service as it was shown that the null hypothesis is rejected. While there is no significant difference on implementation of extracurricular activities when respondents are grouped according to sex and educational attainment as it was shown that the null hypothesis is accepted.

As a result of the study, the researcher would like to recommend the following:

To the School Administrators, they may continue to support their teacher upon implementation of extracurricular activities and ensure that the students' needs are meet.

To the Teachers, they may help to guide the students when participating in extracurricular activities, and sustain interest in the activities. Teachers can use their leadership skills in guiding the participant.

To the Parents, they may help the students to motivate them to be involved in extracurricular activities and help through financial needs.

To the Pupils, they may continue learn to improve their confidence and learn to give importance in participating extracurricular

activities.

To the Future Researchers, they may conduct a parallel study using bigger population for more viable and reliable results.

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